

STUDIES IN ADSORPTION INDICATORS. PART I. RESORCINOL SUCCINEIN AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR IN ARGENTOMETRIC TITRATIONS

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Resorcinol succinein has been used as adsorption indicator in argentometric titrations. It has been found to be a very useful indicator and under certain conditions serves even better than fluorescein.

Following the discovery of Fajans (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1923, 29, 495), an intensive study has been made of phthaleins, sulphophthaleins, rhodamines and a few other dyes for their applicability as adsorption indicators. No attempt seems to have been made so far in applying succinic acid derivatives to these precipitation reactions. It would be of both theoretical and practical interest to try the resorcinol-succinein as an adsorption indicator.

EXPERIMENTAL

Resorcinol-succinein was prepared by the method of Biggs and Pope (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2934) and recrystallised from acid, m. p. 234°. A solution of the pure product (1%) was made in 50% alcohol and one or two drops of the indicator employed for 10 c. c. of the solution throughout the course of this investigation.

Titration of Chloride against Silver Ions.—In this titration the end-point was quite sharp in $N/10$ solution, at the end-point the coagulation of the deep pink coloured precipitate occurred leaving the entire solution colourless. With the $N/100$ solutions the end-point was not so sharp. The end-point could be improved by the use of magnesium nitrate as a coagulating agent. The titration is carried out best at pH 7 using 2 drops of the indicator per 10 c. c. of the solution.

Titration of Sulphocyanide Ions against Silver Ions.—Coagulation of the precipitate began with the first drop of silver nitrate of $N/10$ solution and the precipitate assumed a pinkish shade from the very beginning. This observation is of interest with regard to the conflicting views of Fajans (*loc. cit.*) and Kolthoff (*Chem. Rev.*, 1935, 16, 87; *Kolloid Z.*, 1934, 68, 190). The capacity of the silver sulphocyanide particles to adsorb the succinyl fluorinate ions in presence of a large concentration of sulphocyanide ions is in accordance with the view of Kolthoff according to whom "the colour change is not due to a secondary adsorption of the dye at the active spots, but to an exchange adsorption involving lattice ions of the same electrical sign on the entire surface of the precipitate". At the end-point the colour of the precipitate changed abruptly from light pink to deep pink. The titrations of sulphocyanide can be carried out within 0.5% error up to a dilution of $N/100$. In dilute solutions, the colour change occurred in the homogeneous phase and no coagulation occurred during the course of the titration. The titrations were quite reversible.

Titration of Bromide against Silver Ions.—Quite sharp end-points were obtained up to 0.005 N solutions; with $N/10$ solutions coagulation occurred before

the end-point but the sharp colour change of the precipitate from yellow to pink occurred just at the end-point. In dilute solutions the titrations were quite reversible.

Titration of Iodide against Silver Ions.— $N/4000$ -KI solutions were titrated against $N/1000$ silver nitrate with an accuracy within 1% of the theoretical amount. In $N/10$ solutions coagulation occurred much before the end-point, but the colour change of the precipitate (pinkish yellow to deep pink) occurred just at the end-point. In dilute solution, a sharp colour change occurred in the homogeneous phase with half a drop of the silver ion in excess. When 2 drops of the indicator per 10 c. c. of the solution are used the colour change is better viewed in the reflected light. In dilute solutions, the titration was quite reversible. However, as with all other halides, the titration is not possible in acidic media.

TABLE I

Titration of	With	Dilution.	Transition.	More detailed conditions.
Cl-	Ag+	$N/10$ to $N/20$	Pink yellow soln. to pink ppt.	Soln. neutral or very weakly alkaline. Can be used with fairly high accuracy upto $N/50$ soln. In more dilute soln., the coagulating agents improve the end-point.
CN-	Ag+	$N/10$ to $N/50$	Light pink ppt. to deep pink	Coagulation occurs from the beginning, but a very sharp end-point. Soln. neutral
Br-	Ag+	$N/10$ to $N/50$	Pink yellow ppt. to pink ppt.	Coagulation occurs before the end-point, but the colour change on the ppt. appears just at the end-point. Soln. must be neutral
		$N/50$ to $N/200$	Pinkish yellow soln. to pink ppt.	Colour change occurs in the homogeneous phase and immediately after the ppt. coagulates. Titration quite reversible.
I-	Ag+	$N/10$ to $N/50$	Pink yellow ppt. to Pink ppt.	Coagulation occurs much before the end-point, but a sharp colour change on the ppt. just at the end-point.
		$N/100$	Yellow soln. to pink soln.	Colour change occurs in the homogeneous phase and immediately after pinkish ppt. coagulates.
		$N/100$ to $N/4000$	Yellow soln. to pink soln.	Colour change in the homogeneous phase. Better viewed in the reflected light. Very accurate results possible with a little care.

Comparison with fluorescein.—The new indicator succinyl-fluorescein compares very favourably with the ordinary dye fluorescein in its applicability as adsorption indicator. Its adsorbability is definitely greater than the ordinary fluorescein. This greater adsorbability limits the range of usefulness of this indicator to $N/10$ solutions in the case of chloride ions, but makes it a definitely better indicator for iodide ions where solutions varying from $N/10$ to $N/4000$ can be titrated. The end-point is particularly sharp and quite reversible in dilute solutions, because no signs of coagulation occur there and the colour change appears in the homogeneous phase.

Further work with the indicator is in progress.

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